

MODERN WAYS OF INTEGRATION OF KARAKALPAKIAN JIROV PERFORMANCE INTO MUSICAL-PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES

Nuratdinov Zinatdin Elubaevich

1st year basic doctoral student of Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizami
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Annotation: This thesis covers the issues of integrating the art of jirov performance, which belongs to the rich musical heritage of the Karakalpak people, into modern musical and pedagogical activities. It reveals the role of jirov performance as an aesthetic, educational and cultural value. It also analyzes effective ways of combining it with modern educational programs while preserving the traditional performing school. The thesis proposes methodological approaches aimed at using jirov performance in the professional training of music teachers, practical exercises in the lesson process, forming aesthetic taste through listening, and a deep understanding of national musical culture.

Keywords: Karakalpak jirov performance, musical and pedagogical activities, integration, aesthetic education, performing school, cultural heritage.

Introduction.

The culture, art and values of each nation are considered a reflection of the spiritual world of that nation, a reflection of its national identity. The musical heritage of the Karakalpak people is also an incomparable wealth, and the art of jirov performance, which is an integral part of it, embodies not only our national identity, but also high examples of our musical thinking. In today's globalization, educating the younger generation based on national values, raising them in a spirit of respect for our cultural heritage is one of the urgent tasks. From this perspective, the issue of integrating Karakalpak jirov performance into modern musical and pedagogical activities is distinguished by its relevance. The modern educational process should not be limited only to providing theoretical knowledge, but also serve to form students' attitudes towards national culture, to educate them as people with artistic and aesthetic taste. Therefore, the introduction of jirov performance into musical and pedagogical activities, while preserving the traditions of this ancient art, will allow it to be further revived by incorporating it into the practical educational process. This will serve not only to pass on the musical heritage of Karakalpak to the new generation, but also to improve the quality of education.

The purpose of this thesis is to analyze effective ways to integrate the specific features of the art of Karakalpak jirov performance into musical and

pedagogical activities, to develop methodological foundations for the use of this heritage in the educational system. The main objectives of the thesis are:

Study of the artistic and methodological aspects specific to the art of Karakalpak jirov performance;

Analysis of the possibilities of integrating these performing traditions into the educational system;

Identification of ways to form methodological skills of music teachers and students in this area;

Development of a methodology for the effective use of zhirov performance in musical and aesthetic education.

National heritage is not only the past, but also the foundation for the future. Therefore, by introducing Karakalpak zhirov performance into modern musical and pedagogical activities, we not only preserve our art, but also take it to a new level.

Zhirov performance occupies a special place in the national musical heritage of the Karakalpak people. This art form embodies not only musical melodies, but also the oral creativity of the people, historical memory, spiritual and moral values, beliefs and philosophy of life. Zhirovs are living representatives of the oral epic and song traditions of the Karakalpak people, who have been passing on folk oral creativity from generation to generation through epics, tales, proverbs and legends for years. Today, preserving this invaluable wealth and passing it on to the younger generation, incorporating it into the educational process, remains a requirement of the time.

Musical and pedagogical activity has great potential in this regard. Because it serves not only to form performing skills, but also to strengthen the aesthetic worldview of the individual, national pride, and historical memory. By using examples of jirov performance in the educational process, it is possible to form in students a deep attitude towards music, love for national melodies, and the ability to think based on values.

Several directions for integrating jirov performance into modern musical and pedagogical activities can be indicated. First, this is to teach students the melodic and textual analysis of epics or songs through practical exercises. Second, it is possible to organize mini-master classes in jirov performance based on interactive methods, and to form an active learning environment through practical performance, discussion, individual and group work. The third direction is to encourage students to create their own compositions based on

national music through creative projects, to introduce them to dramaturgy, composition, and means of expression.

Also, in today's era of advanced educational technologies, it is important to integrate examples of jirov performance in audio and video format into the lesson process using digital platforms. This can be an effective tool for forming a culture of listening to music for students, a deep understanding of national music, and arousing interest.

In order to successfully integrate Karakalpak jirov performance into musical and pedagogical activities, first of all, teachers themselves must have deep knowledge and skills in this area. This can be done through special courses, modules, and practical training in higher educational institutions that train pedagogical personnel. Seminars and trainings held in collaboration with regional cultural centers and jirov masters are also of great importance in this area.

Thus, jirov performance is not only a means of musical expression of a people, but also history, philosophy, morality, and spirituality are conveyed to generations through it. Therefore, the application of this invaluable wealth to the educational process is one of the urgent pedagogical tasks that serve to educate the younger generation as a complete person, aimed at the formation of national and cultural identity.

The main requirement of modern musical and pedagogical activities is the formation of education focused on the personal development of the student, based on the harmony of national and universal values. Karakalpak jirov performance is a unique example of musical culture that embodies such values, and its integration into the educational process will not only increase the effectiveness of the educational process, but also serve to form national pride and aesthetic taste in the younger generation.

The results of the analysis show that, although there is currently a movement in Karakalpakstan and Uzbekistan as a whole to include national musical heritage in educational programs, a systematic approach to jirov performance is insufficient. Although classes in this area are held in some music schools or art colleges, they are more based on practice and are not combined with modern pedagogical technologies. Therefore, there is a need to update methodological approaches in this regard and introduce innovative educational technologies.

Based on the analysis conducted during the thesis, it was determined that the pedagogical potential of jirov performance is very high: its strong oral

traditions, musical dramaturgy, intonational richness and expressive styles expand the thinking of young people, form in them the culture of oral speech, stage performance skills, and aesthetic evaluation skills. In particular, by listening to, analyzing, and attempting to perform jirov works during the lesson, students delve deeper into their national musical roots.

In addition, opportunities for studying jirov performance are expanding through independent learning, project-based approaches, and the use of information and communication technologies. Epics, audio recordings, and video performances stored on digital platforms provide teachers and students with new didactic resources. In particular, teaching based on media products not only attracts the attention of the listener, but also allows for the revival of traditional art through modern technologies.

The integration of Karakalpak jirov performance into musical and pedagogical activities is not about restoring the national musical heritage, but also about developing it in line with the times. This requires a new approach, methodological preparation, and initiative aimed at awakening national consciousness from educators. Therefore, each initiative in this direction is not only a part of musical education, but also a part of general cultural development.

Conclusion.

One of the most urgent tasks facing the education sector today is to educate the younger generation in the national spirit, to bring them up in harmony with the rich culture, art and historical heritage of their people. From this point of view, the issue of integrating the performance of Karakalpak jirov into musical and pedagogical activities acquires not only aesthetic, but also socio-spiritual significance. The meaning, melody and means of artistic expression in the performance of jirovs have the power to directly affect the hearts of young people, leading them to a sense of identity.

Using this rich heritage in the educational process serves to expand the musical worldview of students, increase their national pride, and develop their creativity and thinking. The educational and aesthetic potential of jirov works turns them into not only listeners, but also active observers and creative thinkers. This fully corresponds to the modern goals of the education system.

Also, by incorporating this art into the educational process, we do not just remember the past, but also combine it with modern knowledge, technologies and pedagogical approaches. As a result, traditional and modern thinking enrich each other, forming a new educational environment. This demonstrates the harmony of nationality and innovation in practice.

In conclusion, the integration of Karakalpak jirov performance into musical and pedagogical activities is not only about bringing innovation to music lessons, but also about awakening the spirit of the nation through education, educating in the spirit of respect for cultural heritage, and forming national identity through art. This is the most powerful means of instilling love for musical heritage not only in the hearts of educators, but also in the hearts of every member of society.

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